
Trend Analysis of Seasonal Rainfall in Pune Division of Maharashtra State.

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Abstract:

Climate change significantly influences rainfall patterns globally and in regionally as like Pune division in Maharashtra. Climate change has led to changes in rainfall intensity, frequency, and distribution. It can disrupt traditional monsoon patterns and trend causing erratic rainfall during the season. Uneven distribution of rainfall can lead to periods of heavy rain followed by dry spells, affecting agriculture and water resources.

In this research work, we have analysed the temporal trend of seasonal rainfall (June to September) in Pune division of Maharashtra state during 2023 and 2024 years. Trend analysis of seasonal rainfall in Pune division of Maharashtra state was analyzed using non-parametric Mann-Kendall test, with 95 percent confidence levels. Pune division comprises five districts i.e. Pune, Satara, Solapur, Sangli, and Kolhapur districts. The rainfall trend in Pune division of Maharashtra generally follows the typical monsoonal pattern of the region. These data analysis shows that rainfall patterns have experienced variations over the years, with some years having above-average rainfall and others experiencing deficits.

Keywords: Climate Change, Seasonal Rainfall Trend, Pattern, Mann-Kendall, Sen's slope.

Introduction:

Climate is indeed one of the most critical environmental factors, as it influences nearly every aspect of natural systems, human life, and economic activities. As a global regulator, climate maintains Earth's heat balance and drives essential systems like monsoons. The role of climate is vital for ensuring environmental sustainability and human resilience.

The hydrological cycle and regional crop pattern may be significantly impacted by the altered rainfall patterns brought on by climate change (Mirza and Hussain 2003; David Chikodzi and Linda Yeukai Mapfaka, 2018; Abrol et al., 2004). One of the key meteorological factors for identifying climate change is rainfall (Sahu and Khare, 2015).

Numerous scholars such as Naidu et al., 1999; Guhathakurta and Rajeevan, 2008; Kumar et al., 2010; Gosain et al., 2011; Joshi and Pandey, 2011 and Naveen Kumar et al. 2016 have examined the seasonal and annual patterns of rainfall in India at the regional level.

India is agricultural nation with high percentage of its population dependent on agriculture, is particularly susceptible to the effects of climate hazards. Sometime in the semi-arid areas of Western India received more rainfall than normal due to temperature rise. The development of future climate scenarios will benefit from the trend analysis of temperature, precipitation, and other climatic variables on various regional scales (Jain et al., 2012).

In the sense of impact of climate change Maharashtra state is one of the key states. The geographical area of Maharashtra state is 307,713 square kilometres (30.7 Mha) out of which, 73.29 percent is cultivable, 40 percent drought prone and 7 percent flood prone area. About rainfall it is uneven rainfall ranging from 400 to 4500 mm occurs with from 40 to 100 rainy days in the State. The state experiences a tropical monsoon climate, with distinct wet and dry seasons, but there is considerable variability in rainfall across different regions because of the uneven terrain and proximity to the coast.

This research works has been analysed seasonal rainfall trend of the years 2023 and 2024 in Pune divisions of Maharashtra state. Trend analysis of seasonal rainfall in Pune division of Maharashtra state was analyzed using non-parametric Mann-Kendall and Sen's slope test, with 95 percent and 99 percent confidence levels. Pune division comprises five districts i.e. Pune, Satara, Solapur, Sangli, and Kolhapur districts. The rainfall trend in Pune division of Maharashtra generally follows the typical monsoonal pattern of the region. These data analysis shows that rainfall patterns have experienced variations over the years, with some years having above-average rainfall and others experiencing deficits.

Objectives of the Study:

The current research study has been undertaken with the following objective

1. To find out trends of seasonal rainfall in study area.

Study Region:

The Pune Division, situated in the western region of Maharashtra, India, encompasses five distinct districts: Pune, Solapur, Satara, Sangli, and Kolhapur. This division is geographically delineated by the Konkan region to the west, the Nashik Division to the north, Marathwada to the east, and the state of Karnataka to the south.

Pune city functions as the administrative center for both the Pune District and Pune Division. Referred to as the "Oxford of the East," Pune is distinguished for its prestigious educational institutions and rich cultural heritage. The geographical diversity of the division encompasses metropolitan areas, agrarian landscapes, and undulating topographies, which collectively enhance its heterogeneous climate and abundant biodiversity. From an economic perspective, the Pune Division holds considerable significance owing to its industrial sectors, centres of education, and cultural heritage sites.

Data Collection and Methodology:

This research is based on the secondary source of information of the Department of Agriculture, Maharashtra State. (<https://maharain.maharashtra.gov.in/>). The study is related to the trend analysis of seasonal rainfall in Pune division of Maharashtra. In this research work, we have taken district wise seasonal rainfall data of pune division i.e. 2023 and 2024 of Maharashtra. The pune division of Maharashtra state comprises Pune, Satara, Solapur, Sangli, and Kolhapur districts.

To analyze data, various appropriate trend analysis tools have been used non-parametric Mann-Kendall tests, with 95 percent confidence levels. The maps and diagrams are prepared by adopting various cartographic techniques it includes bar and line graphs for better comprehension.

Mann-Kendall (MK) test:

The **Mann-Kendall (MK) test** is a non-parametric statistical test used to identify trends in time-series data. It is widely used in environmental sciences, hydrology, climatology, and related fields to detect whether there is a significant increasing or decreasing trend in data over time. (Mann 1945; Kendall 1975).

Equation (1) defines the MK statistics (S)

$$S = \sum_{b=1}^{n-1} \sum_{c=b+1}^n \text{sign}(X_c - X_b)$$

Where:

X_b and X_c are the seasonal values in years b and c .

The later observations in the time series tend to be bigger than the earlier observations if $S > 0$, and the opposite is true if $S < 0$.

Equation (2)

$$\text{Sign}(X_b - X_c) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } X_c - X_b > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } X_c - X_b = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } X_c - X_b < 0 \end{cases}$$

Equation (3) is used to compute the variance of S :

$$\text{var}(S) = \frac{1}{18} \left[n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{p=1}^q f_p(f_p-1)(2f_p+5) \right]$$

where n is the number of data points, q is the number of tied groups, and f_p is the number of data values in the q^{th} group.

Equation (4) if no tied is used to compute the variance of S :

$$\text{var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18}$$

where n is the number of data points,

Equation (5) is used to determine the test statistics Z using the values of S and $\text{var}(S)$.

$$Z = \begin{cases} (S-1)/S_r & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0 \\ (S+1)/S_r & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases}$$

Table No.1: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during June 2023.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	3.02	0	13.7	4.9	162	0.004043	2.6104	Increase
Solapur	0.96	0	11.4	2.2	232	0.008845	2.618	Increase
Satara	2.86	0	18.4	4.8	168	0.04114	2.0421	Increase
Sangli	1.19	0	8	2.0	169	0.247	1.1576	Increase
Kolhapur	3.26	0	19.3	5.1	163	0.006538	2.7195	Increase

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of June 2023:

The average rainfall in June month is given in table no.1 with district wise of pune division. The highest average rainfall was observed at Kolhapur district (3.26 ± 5.1 mm) with 163 % coefficient of variation and lowest at Solapur (0.96 ± 2.2 mm) with 232 percent a coefficient of variation.

where s_r is the square root of $\text{var}(S)$.

The **Mann-Kendall (MK) test** result is primarily determined by the **p-value**, which indicates the statistical significance of a trend in a time series. The **p-value** represents the probability that the observed trend is due to random chance. A **lower p-value** suggests that the trend is more likely to be real and not due to randomness.

The concluded the trend, if $p \leq \alpha$ (Significance Level i.e. 90, 95, 99 percent) **reject the null hypothesis** (H_0) it means A significant trend exists (either increasing or decreasing). and if $p > \alpha$ (Significance Level i.e. 90, 95, 99 percent) **fail to reject H_0** it means No significant trend detected.

The checking Trend Direction with Z-Score of Mann-Kendall Statistical Techniques, If the Mann-Kendall Z-score is positive \rightarrow Upward trend (increasing) and if the Mann-Kendall Z-score is negative \rightarrow Downward trend (decreasing).

Results and Discussion:

The rainfall trends were identified by using Mann Kendal Test estimator method on Seasonal Rainfall with Month wise for 2023 and 2024 years of Pune division.

Rainfall in five districts of Pune division for the two years 2023 and 2024 has been analyzed to identify the rainfall trends based on availability of data.

In this month of June 2023, P-value of Sangli district has greater than 0.05 confidence level i.e. 0.247. It means Sangli district has found *no significant increase trend* of rainfall and other district of pune division has *significant increase trend* of rainfall in the month of June 2023.

Table No. 2: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during July 2023.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	9.07	0.8	23.6	6.7	73	0.4859	1.9722	Increase
Solapur	5.80	0	33.2	7.9	136	0.01123	2.5355	Increase
Satara	9.84	1.1	32.4	8.1	82	0.06146	1.8701	Increase
Sangli	5.55	0.1	19.4	5.2	94	0.003419	2.9273	Increase
Kolhapur	19.40	2.1	49	14.1	73	0.06893	1.8189	Increase

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of July 2023:

The average rainfall in July month is given in table no. 2 with district wise of pune division. The highest average rainfall was observed at Kolhapur district (19.40 ± 14.4 mm) with 73% coefficient of variation followed by Satara and Pune district and lowest at Sangli (5.55 ± 5.2 mm) with 94 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month of July 2023, P-value of Pune, Satara and Kolhapur district has greater than 0.05 confidence level i.e. 0.4859, 0.06146 and 0.06893 respectively. it indicates these districts has found *no significant increase trend* of rainfall and other district of pune division such as Solapur and Sangli has *significant increase trend* of rainfall in the month of July 2023.

Table No. 3: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during August 2023.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	2.78	0.1	7.9	1.9	70	0.05651	1.9071	Increase
Solapur	0.65	0	3.6	0.9	131	0.6062	0.51553	Increase
Satara	2.59	0	9.3	2.3	90	0.001379	-3.199	Decrease
Sangli	1.07	0	6.1	1.2	114	0.01753	-2.3755	Decrease
Kolhapur	4.26	0.1	15.3	4.3	100	0.003253	-2.9428	Decrease

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of August 2023:

The average rainfall in August month is given in table no. 3 with district wise of pune division. In this month the highest average rainfall was observed at Kolhapur district (4.26 ± 4.3 mm) with 100 % coefficient of variation followed by Pune and Satara district and lowest at Solapur (0.65 ± 0.9 mm) with 131 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month of August 2023, P-value of Pune and Solapur district has greater than 0.05 confidence level i.e. 0.05651 and 0.6062 respectively. it means these districts has found *no significant increase trend* of rainfall and other district of pune division such as Satara, Sangli and Kolhapur has *significant Decrease trend* of rainfall in the month of August 2023.

Table No. 4: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during September 2023.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	6.63	0	24.4	6.7	101	0.003838	2.8912	Increase
Solapur	4.63	0	15.5	6.2	134	0.2112	1.2502	Increase
Satara	3.62	0	15.6	3.9	107	0.03197	2.1448	Increase
Sangli	3.75	0	26	5.8	153	0.03646	2.0917	Increase
Kolhapur	4.87	0	22.8	5.6	117	0.02329	2.2686	Increase

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of September 2023:

The average rainfall in September month is given in table no. 4 with district wise of pune division. In this month the highest average rainfall was observed at Pune district (6.63 ± 6.7 mm) with 101 % coefficient of variation followed by Kolhapur and Solapur district and lowest at Satara

(3.62 ± 3.9 mm) with 107 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month of September 2023, P-value of Solapur district has greater than 0.05 confidence level i.e. 0.2112. it is represented this district has found *no significant increase trend* of rainfall and other district of Pune division such as Pune, Satara, Sangli and Kolhapur has *significant Increase trend* of rainfall in the month of September 2023.

Table No. 5: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during June 2024.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	5.71	0	16.4	7.2	126	0.9858	-0.017857	Decrease
Solapur	7.61	0	32.7	10.6	139	0.01845	-2.3565	Decrease
Satara	7.94	0	51.8	11.5	145	0.544	0.60679	Increase
Sangli	7.54	0	34	9.1	121	0.4428	-0.76753	Decrease
Kolhapur	6.69	0	32.9	8.1	121	0.004521	2.8393	Increase

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of June 2024:

The average rainfall in June month is given in table no. 5 with district wise of pune division. In this month the highest average rainfall was observed at Satara district (7.94 ± 11.5 mm) with 145 % coefficient of variation followed by Solapur and Sangli district and lowest at Pune (5.71 ± 7.2 mm) with 126 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month of September 2023, P-value of Pune and Satara district has greater than 0.05 confidence level i.e. 0.9858 and 0.544 respectively with *no significant decrease trend* of rainfall and *no significant Increase trend* of rainfall respectively. other district of Pune division such as Solapur and Sangli has *significant decrease trend* of rainfall and Kolhapur has *significant increase trend* in the month of June 2024.

Table No. 6: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during July 2024.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	14.30	0.7	89.7	17	119	0.05918	1.8869	Increase
Solapur	3.99	0.1	19.9	5.3	133	0.7853	-0.27247	Decrease
Satara	15.65	0.4	3.2	13.1	84	0.005035	2.8048	Increase
Sangli	9.15	0.3	40	9.9	108	0.1131	2.5328	Increase
Kolhapur	25.77	1.2	69.7	16.7	65	0.01026	2.5668	Increase

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of July 2024:

The average rainfall in July month is given in table no. 6 with district wise of pune division. In this month the highest average rainfall was observed at Kolhapur district (25.77 ± 16.7 mm) with 65 % coefficient of variation followed by Satara and Pune district and lowest at Solapur (3.99 ± 5.3 mm) with 133 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month of July 2024, P-value of Pune and Solapur district has greater than 0.05 confidence level i.e. *0.9858 and 0.544 respectively with no significant increase trend of rainfall and no significant decrease trend of rainfall respectively.* other district of Pune division such as Satara, Sangli and Kolhapur has *significant increase trend of rainfall.*

Table No. 7: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during August 2024.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	9.76	0	34.5	9.6	98	0.8918	-0.13601	Decrease
Solapur	4.02	0	33.6	6.3	157	0.9322	0.085109	Increase
Satara	9.09	0.3	33.7	9.1	100	0.6708	0.42509	Increase
Sangli	7.14	0.3	27.8	7.5	105	0.2475	1.1564	Increase
Kolhapur	10.89	0	35.6	10.8	99	0.8784	-0.15299	Decrease

Note: significant trend at the 95% confidence level

Rainfall Trend for Month of August 2024:

The average rainfall in August month is given in table no. 7 with district wise of pune division. In this month the highest average rainfall was observed at Kolhapur district (10.89 ± 10.8 mm) with 99 % coefficient of variation and lowest at Solapur (4.02 ± 6.3 mm) with 157 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month, P-value has greater than 0.05 confidence level at whole Pune division of Maharashtra state with Pune and Kolhapur has *no significant decrease trend of rainfall and remaining other district of Pune division such as Solapur, Satara and Sangli has no significant increase trend of rainfall.*

Table No. 8: Rainfall Trend in Pune Division during September 2024.

Name of District	Mean (mm)	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)	P Value	Z Value	Trend
Pune	4.51	0	25.3	5.9	131	0.9146	-0.10721	Decrease
Solapur	4.85	0	24.8	6.9	142	0.3591	-0.91707	Decrease
Satara	4.11	0	21.5	5.7	139	0.9857	-0.01787	Decrease
Sangli	4.68	0	28.4	7.3	92	0.2179	-1.2321	Decrease
Kolhapur	4.69	0.2	18.7	4.5	96	0.1005	-1.6424	Decrease

Rainfall Trend for Month of September 2024:

The average rainfall in September month is given in table no. 8 with district wise of pune division. In this month the highest average rainfall was observed at Kolhapur district (4.69 ± 4.5 mm) with 96 % coefficient of variation and lowest at Satara (4.11 ± 5.7 mm) with 139 percent of a coefficient of variation.

In this month, P-value has greater than 0.05 confidence level at whole Pune division of Maharashtra state has *no significant decrease trend* of rainfall.

Conclusion:

The average Seasonal rainfall distribution over the Pune division is uneven throughout the years. Generally, according to above finding the highest average seasonally rainfall in 2023 and 2024 years during the months in June to September remain in Kolhapur District.

In the year of 2023 sangli in June; Pune, Satara and Kolhapur in July; Pune and Solapur in August; and Solapur in September has found no significant increase trend in Rainfall.

So, Pune, Satara, Solapur and Kolhapur in June; Solapur and Sangli in July has significance increase trend in rainfall; Satara, Sangli and Kolhapur in August has significance decrease trend in rainfall and Pune, Satara, Sangli and Kolhapur in September has significant increase trend in rainfall.

In the year of 2024, Satara in June; Pune in July; and Solapur, Satara and Sangli in has found no significant increase trend in Rainfall and Pune in June; Solapur in July; Pune and Kolhapur; and all district of pune division in September has found no significant decrease trend in Rainfall

So, Kolhapur in June; Kolhapur, Satara and Sangli in July has significance increase trend in rainfall; Solapur and Sangli

district in June has significance decrease trend in rainfall.

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